

Ability to assess claims about treatment effects among bachelor students in health sciences: a protocol for feasibility testing a course in Evidence-Based Health Care

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Abstract

Background

Various health claims about products, remedies, and treatments are everywhere, and many fail to assess these claims. It is therefore important to enable people to think critically about such claims. Oslo Metropolitan University (OsloMet) developed and implemented an educational intervention as a part of a mandatory course in Evidence-Based Health Care (EBHC) for bachelor students in health sciences to increase their critical thinking skills by enabling them to critically assess health claims about treatment effects in the media and make informed choices. A relevant next step is feasibility testing of the EBHC course.

Objective

This protocol describes the plan of testing and adjusting methods to assess effects of an educational intervention in skills to assess health claims. In particular the assessment methods' feasibility, reliability and validity will be investigated. Feasibility applied to the evaluation tool refers to acceptance by students of a following efficacy trial. Reliability will be investigated in terms unidimensionality of the underpinning construct, while validity refers to the ability of the evaluation tool to detect effect achieved by the training intervention (responsiveness).

Participants, methods, and analysis

Eligible participants will be bachelor students in health sciences at OsloMet attending the EBHC course. Participants in sub-study 1 and 2 were recruited in 2020/21 and 2021/22. Participants for sub-study 3 and 4 will be recruited during autumn 2022.

Both quantitative and qualitative methods will be used to feasibility test the intervention. We will use generalised linear models from cross-sectional surveys and thematic analysis of open-ended questions from cross-sectional surveys and focus group interviews to assess the acceptance of the EBHC course among students (sub-study 1). We will use Rasch analysis to evaluate the psychometric properties of the questionnaires from cross-sectional surveys (sub-study 2 and 3). Generalised linear models will be used to estimate learning outcome from uncontrolled before-after studies (sub-study 4).

Ethical considerations

The studies to be carried out in 2022 were approved by the Norwegian Centre for Research Data (NSD) on 28 July 2022 (Reference number 935258).

Background

Conflicting health claims constantly occur in the media and on social media (Haber et al., 2018; Walsh-Childers et al., 2018). The overload of conflicting health information is especially challenging during major disease outbreaks, where both correct, incorrect, and misleading information flourishes. The World Health Organization (WHO) has called the overload of information related to the Covid-19 pandemic an “infodemic” (World Health Organization, 2021). At all time, not only during pandemics, multiple media news reports provide a simplified and biased picture of the possible effects of interventions, and they often do not provide information about conflict of interest, possible harms, and costs (Oxman et al., 2021).

Many Norwegian adults find it challenging to understand health information (Le C et al., 2021), and many do not have the ability to critically assess health claims (Austvoll-Dahlgren et al., 2020b; Oxman et al., 2017). Consequently, it is important to enable people to think critically about health claims. However, there is no agreement on the definition and conceptualisation of critical thinking (Lai, 2011; Moore, 2013; Thonney & Montgomery, 2019). Critical thinking is both a component of health literacy (Sørensen et al., 2012) which refers to skills that enable individuals to find, understand and use information to make decisions and take actions that affect their health (Nutbeam et al., 2018), and of critical assessment that illuminates how to use research evidence to make informed health decisions (Gambrill, 2006; Profetto-McGrath, 2005; Sharples et al., 2017). Critical assessment is closely related to Nutbeam’s definition of critical health literacy (Oxman & García, 2020) in his three-level model of functional, interactive, and critical health literacy (Nutbeam, 2000). In this model, critical health literacy refers to more advanced cognitive and social skills needed to critically assess health information and use this to exert greater control over situations which may impact their health (Nutbeam, 2000).

Consequences of action on deficient or misleading information about effect and side effects can be both harmful and costly, by overusing ineffective treatment (Brownlee et al., 2017) and underusing effective treatment (Glasziou et al., 2017). Thus, people need to be able to critically assess the reliability of health claims about treatment effects in order to make well-informed health decisions (Sharples et al., 2017). Claims about treatment effects refer to strategies to prevent illness, such as changes in health behaviour, therapeutic interventions, or public health interventions (Chalmers et al., 2018). A claim about treatment effects is thus something someone says about whether a treatment leads to something happening or changing, i.e., a causal relationship (Austvoll-Dahlgren et al., 2017). However, there is no agreement on the conceptualisation and concepts that are necessary to assess the effect of treatments. In addition, people’s understanding of the effect of treatments is not measured consistently because the field is characterised by parallel discourses that use different terminology (Austvoll-Dahlgren et al., 2015).

In an attempt to address these challenges, the Informed Health Choices (IHC) project developed and evaluated resources that enable people to understand and apply important concepts needed to critically assess claims about treatment effects and make informed health choices (Austvoll-Dahlgren et al., 2015; Chalmers et al., 2018). This includes the IHC Key Concepts framework (Table 1) (Oxman et al., 2022), which are principles for evaluating the reliability of claims about treatment effect that are relevant for young people, patients and public, policymakers, and health professionals (Oxman & García, 2020). The IHC Key Concept framework was developed in a stepwise process of reviewing the literature and consulting a broad advisory group (Austvoll-Dahlgren et al., 2015; Oxman et al., 2019). The learning material is not an intervention itself, but it can be used to develop educational interventions (Informed Health Choices, 2019; Oxman et al., 2019).

Table 1. Nine high-level concepts (IHC Key Concepts framework)

1. Claims <i>Claims about effects that are not supported by evidence from fair comparisons are not necessarily wrong, but there is an insufficient basis for believing them.</i>	2. Comparisons <i>Studies should make fair comparisons, designed to minimise the risk of systematic errors (biases) and random errors (the play of chance).</i>	3. Choices <i>What to do depends on judgements about a problem, the relevance of the available evidence, and the balance of expected benefits, harms, and costs.</i>
1.1 Assumptions that treatments are safe or effective can be misleading.	2.1 Comparisons of treatments should be fair.	3.1 Evidence should be relevant.
1.2 Seemingly logical assumptions about <u>research</u> can be misleading.	2.2 Reviews of the effects of treatments should be fair.	3.2 Expected advantages should outweigh expected disadvantages.
1.3 Seemingly logical assumptions about <u>treatments</u> can be misleading.	2.3 Descriptions of effects should clearly reflect <u>the size of the effects</u>.	
1.4 Trust based on the source of a claim alone can be misleading.	2.4 Descriptions of effects should reflect <u>the risk of being misled by the play of chance</u>.	

Source: (Oxman et al., 2022)

Based on the IHC Key Concept framework, the Claim Evaluation Tools item bank, consisting of multiple-choice questions for each IHC Key Concept, was developed to assess objectively the understanding of the concepts (Austvoll-Dahlgren et al., 2017). The Claim Evaluation Tool has been evaluated using Rasch modelling and found suitable for use in measuring outcomes related to assessment of treatment claims (Austvoll-Dahlgren et al., 2017).

The Claim Evaluation Tool was developed because there was a need for an instrument that assessed people's overall ability to assess claims about treatment effects, especially their ability to use key concepts needed to do so (Austvoll-Dahlgren et al., 2016). An example of a MCQ from the Claim Evaluation Tool database is presented in Figure 1.

Judith wants smoother skin. The younger girls in her school have smoother skin than the older girls. Judith thinks this is because the younger girls use cream on their skin to make the skin smoother.

Question: Based on this link between using cream and smooth skin, is Judith correct?

Options:

- A) It is not possible to say. It depends on how many younger and older girls there are.
- B) It is not possible to say. There might be other differences between the younger and older girls.
- C) Yes, because the younger girls use cream on their skin, and they have smoother skin.
- D) No, Judith should try using the cream herself to see if it works for her.

Figure 1. Example of multiple-choice question from the Claim Evaluation Tool (Do not assume that association is the same as causation).

The Claim Evaluation Tool also includes questions about intended behaviour and attitudes. The questions about intended behaviour, i.e., how likely it is for the respondents to act based on health claims, are to be ranked on a scale from very unlikely to very likely, and “I don’t know”, example in Figure 2. In the questions about attitudes, the respondents should judge how easy or difficult they find it to find and assess health claims. The answer options range from very difficult to very easy, and “I don’t know”. There is no right or wrong answer to the questions about intended behaviour and attitudes.

Think about a sickness that you might get. Imagine someone claiming (saying) that a treatment might help you get better.

4.5 Question: How likely are you to find out what the claim was based on (for example by asking the person making the claim)?

Options:

- Very unlikely
- Unlikely
- Likely
- Very likely
- I don't know

Figure 2. Example of a question about intended behaviour from the Claim Evaluation Tool

The educational intervention “Behind the headlines”

In 2018, Oslo Metropolitan University (OsloMet) developed in a collaboration between students, teachers, and researchers an educational intervention based on five key concepts (Table 2, marked

with green) from the IHC framework, called "Behind the headlines"

(<https://bakoverskriftene.oslomet.no/about/>). "Behind the headlines" used simple and recognizable health claims about treatment effects from the media to teach bachelor students to think critically about health claims (Oxman et al., 2020).

Table 2. Overview of key concepts used in "Behind the headlines"

1. Claims <i>Claims about effects that are not supported by evidence from fair comparisons are not necessarily wrong, but there is an insufficient basis for believing them.</i>	2. Comparisons <i>To identify treatment effects, studies should make fair comparisons, designed to minimise the risk of systematic errors (biases) and random errors (the play of chance).</i>	3. Choices <i>What to do depends on judgements about a problem, the relevance of the available evidence, and a balance of expected benefits, harms, and costs.</i>
1.2. Seemingly logical assumptions about <i>research</i> can be misleading.	2.4. Description of effects should reflect <i>the risk of being misled by the play of chance</i> .	3.1. Evidence should be relevant.
Do not assume that:	Be cautious of:	Consider the relevance of:
a) a plausible explanation is sufficient	a) small studies	c) fair comparisons in laboratories, animals, or highly selected people
b) association is the same as causation		
d) a single study is sufficient		

(the full table of all the 49 key concepts in the three main groups and 10 subgroups can be found here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6611932> (Oxman et al., 2022)).

"Behind the headlines" was considered useful as a stepping-stone for learning evidence-based practice (Oxman et al., 2020), and a modified version (Figure 3) of the original intervention was implemented as a part of a newly created and mandatory course in Evidence-based practice (EBP) in health care (hereafter called the EBHC course) for all bachelor students in health sciences at OsloMet from the academic year 2020/21 (Oxman et al., 2020).

Figure 3. The modified "Behind the headlines" module in the EBHC course

The EBHC course

In short, the EBHC course (Figure 4) uses a flipped classroom design where students are instructed to review learning material consisting of text and links to videos and external sources, in "Canvas" (the learning management system used by OsloMet), before attending digital or face-to-face lectures. The digital lecture with student-active learning in groups in "Behind the headlines" is the first topic in the

course, and thus frames the content. Further, the following topics cover all aspects in evidence-based practice (EBP): ask, acquire, appraise and interpret, apply, and evaluate. Health claims from the media are used in all the different steps of EBP. Alongside, already from the start of the course, students are divided into exam groups. In the exam assignments, the students choose and use a health claim to illustrate one or two of the key concepts taught in “Behind the headlines”. A more comprehensive outline of the EBHC course will be provided in a subsequent article.

Figure 4. An overview of the EBHC course

Evaluation of complex interventions

Complex interventions, such as the EBHC course, require the use of multiple research methods to be thoroughly evaluated. A relevant framework in this context is the updated Medical Research Council framework for complex interventions, (Skivington et al., 2021). The model consists of several phases, from development, feasibility, and evaluation, to implementation (Skivington et al., 2021). The research program can start at any phase, and it might be required to go back and forth between the phases if problems or uncertainties are discovered (Skivington et al., 2021). The development of “Behind the headlines” and implementation of the modified version of “Behind the headlines” in the EBHC course is described in Oxman et al. (Oxman et al., 2020). According to Oxman et al., the next step should be feasibility testing of the EBHC course (Oxman et al., 2020).

Objective

This protocol describes the plan of testing and adjusting methods to assess effects of an educational intervention in skills to assess health claims. In particular the assessment methods' feasibility, reliability and validity will be investigated. Feasibility applied to the evaluation tool refers to acceptance by students of a following efficacy trial. Reliability will be investigated in terms unidimensionality of the underpinning construct, while validity refers to the ability of the evaluation tool to detect effect achieved by the training intervention (responsiveness).

Methods

Multiple methods will be used to test the feasibility of the intervention: 1) assessment of acceptability of the intervention in a cross-sectional survey and through focus group interviews, 2) piloting a first draft of the questionnaire for measuring outcomes related to assessment of treatment claims in a cross-sectional survey, 3) piloting a second draft of the questionnaire for measuring outcomes related to assessment of treatment claims in a cross-sectional survey, 4) assessment of learning outcome in an uncontrolled before-after study.

Sub-study 1: Assessment of acceptability of the intervention

During the academic years of 2020/21 and 2021/22, cross-sectional surveys were conducted among the bachelor students who participated in the EBHC course. The anonymous data collections were handled by questionnaires created with nettskjema.no, a survey solution developed and hosted by the University of Oslo (nettskjema@usit.uio.no). In addition, focus group interviews were conducted among students in 2020/21. To find whether the EBHC course is acceptable to the students, we will use data from the cross-sectional evaluation questionnaires and from the focus group interviews.

Setting

Eligible participants were first- and second-year bachelor students at the Faculty of Health at OsloMet. The cross-sectional survey was conducted after the three-weeks EBHC course at OsloMet during the study years of 2020/21 and 2021/22. Individual courses were held for physiotherapy, occupational therapy, bioengineering, and social education, respectively. Announcement of participation in the survey was posted on "Canvas" the day before or on the same day as the course ended, and a reminder was posted after 4-7 days. Participation was voluntary and anonymous, but those who completed the survey could participate in a lucky draw to win a gift card of NOK 500. There was no possible link between the submitted answers and the e-mail-addresses.

Invitation to the focus group interview were announced through "Canvas" towards the end of the EBHC courses and participants were selected by convenience. The one-hour focus group interviews

were conducted via Zoom; three from September to November 2020, and one in March 2021. Each participant received a gift card of NOK 300.

Data collection and analysis

Cross-sectional survey

A cross-sectional survey, with data collections handled by anonymous questionnaires created with nettskjema.no, a survey solution developed and hosted by the University of Oslo (nettskjema@usit.uio.no), was used after completion of the EBHC course in the academic years of 2020/21 and 2021/22. The questionnaire contained several sections, including background information (gender, age, and study program), and a course evaluation section with Likert scale questions, and open-ended questions.

Two questions related to course information and learning outcome were to be ranked from one (bad) to four (very good). The learning outcome was further elaborated in nine questions, where the students ranked their degree of agreement from 1 (strongly disagree) to 6 (strongly agree), in addition to one option for “do not know”. We will dichotomise the students’ responses and analyse the answers separately for each question using generalised linear models.

The evaluation questionnaires also contained open-ended questions where the students were encouraged to provide positive reactions to the course and suggestions for improving the course. We will use thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006) to analyse the responses.

Focus group interviews

The focus group interviews were used to capture the students’ experiences with, and self-assessed value of the EBHC course. Rosenbaum’s adaption of Morville’s Honeycomb framework was used to develop the interview guide (Morville, 2004; Rosenbaum, 2010). The framework contributes to different aspects of problems being covered in the interview, and it distinguishes between seven facets of user experience: usefulness, usability, desirability, findability, accessibility, credibility, and value. The focus group interviews were not tape recorded. Notes were taken by one researcher during the interviews and checked by the moderator afterwards. The participants did not provide feedback on the notes. We will analyse the results using thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006), and the interviews will be coded by one researcher and cross checked by another, and then marked according to the instructions for the adapted Honeycomb framework (Cochrane Norway, 2021).

Sub-study 2: Piloting a first draft of the questionnaire

During the academic years of 2020/21 and 2021/22, cross-sectional surveys were conducted among the bachelor students who participated in the EBHC course. The anonymous data collections were handled by questionnaires created with nettskjema.no, a survey solution developed and hosted by the University of Oslo (nettskjema@usit.uio.no).

Eligible participants were first- and second-year bachelor students at the Faculty of Health at OsloMet who specialised in physiotherapy, occupational therapy, bioengineer, and social education. Individual courses were held for the various health disciplines, and all eligible students were encouraged to participate in the survey through announcements in the university's password protected learning management system "Canvas". Invitation to the survey was posted one to three days before the start of the course, and no reminder was given. Participation in the survey was voluntary and anonymous. However, those who completed the survey could participate in a lucky draw to win a gift card of NOK 500 if they sent an e-mail to one of the researchers. There was no possible link between the submitted answers and the e-mail-addresses. A total of 410 students were enrolled in the EBHC courses in the academic year 2020/21 and 918 students were enrolled in the EBHC courses in the academic year 2021/22. The survey contained several sections, including background information (gender, age, and study specialisation) and twelve questions from the Claim Evaluation Tool database. We will analyse the students' answers using Rasch modelling in RUMM2030. If irregularities are discovered, corrections should be made to the questionnaire and it must be tested again (Boone, 2016).

Rasch analysis

Rasch analysis can be used when a set of questionnaire items is to be summed together to give a total score (which may include several subscale totals, as well as a total score), and to develop outcome measurement tools in a dynamic way (Boone, 2016; Tennant & Conaghan, 2007). In our study, we will apply the Rasch model using the RUMM2030 software, and we will follow the basic aspects of the Rasch analysis (Tennant & Conaghan, 2007).

Overall and individual Item-Person Interaction

We will explore the class interval structure (number and size of ability groups) of the sample using the summary statistics function in RUMM2030, where the ratio between items should be constant across ability groups.

The item-person interaction is presented on a logit scale, and the mean item location in RUMM2030 is always "0". When the instrument is well targeted, i.e., not too easy or too difficult, the mean location for persons will be around the value of zero (Tennant & Conaghan, 2007). A person location value higher than zero indicates that the test is easy and a value lower than zero indicates that the test is difficult (Tennant & Conaghan, 2007). We will report the quality of targeting, i.e., how well targeted the test is to our population.

The item and person Fit Residual Statistics is based on chi-square statistics, and RUMM2030 has a residual statistic (Tennant & Conaghan, 2007). This is the standardised sum of all differences between observed and expected values summed across all subjects, reported as an estimated z-score, which represents a standardized normal distribution. Ideally, item and person fit should have a mean of zero and a standard deviation (SD) of one, although a SD up to 1.4 is accepted.

We will further explore each individual item and person fit. We consider items and persons with significant (at 0.01 significance level) Chi-square probabilities and +/- 2.5 fit residual range as potentially problematic and subject to further analysis. Possible reasons for person misfit are that respondents guesses, copies or provide “too perfect responses” such as ticking all “A” options in the questionnaire. Persons with misfits will be judged for removal from the analysis because these responses may skew the analysis.

When data fit the Rasch model, ability is measured consistently across the trait level scale with low measurement error, implying reliability. This is given as the Person-Separation-Index and indicates the power of the construct to distinguish between high and low ability people. A value of 0.7 will be considered an accepted level of the Person-Separation-Index.

[Identifying MCQs with misfit: Item Characteristic Curve and Differential Item Functioning](#)

The Rasch model's theoretically expected probability of responding correctly as a function of ability on the latent trait scale is indicated as the Item Characteristic Curve (ICC). The curve represents the expected scores, and the dots represents the observed scores for each ability class interval. A good fit is indicated when the observed scores follow the expected values. Measurement errors are indicated for items with a suboptimal fit, for example over-discriminating, under-discriminating, or one or more ability groups deviating. Over-discriminating items may not be a problem, and these items will be considered along with other findings from the analysis. Some Rasch methodologists even argue that these are ideal items since they separate high and low ability people very "strictly". Under-discriminating items do not add to the measurement and should be considered for removal. We will inspect the ICC for all items individually and items with misfits will be considered for removal or repair.

The ICC analysis can also be used to identify Differential Item Function (DIF). Ideally, except for the ability to assess treatment claims, the MCQs in the Claim Evaluation Tool database are expected to perform similarly for males and females, and across age groups. There are two types of DIF: uniform and non-uniform (Tennant & Conaghan, 2007). Uniform DIF is when the difference between groups on an item is systematic, for example older adults having higher ability compared to younger adults on an item. This is less problematic than non-uniform DIF where the difference between groups on an item is inconsistent across ability groups. Items with non-uniform DIF will be considered for removal.

[Tests of multi-dimensionality and local dependency](#)

The Rasch model assumes that the items measure the same underlying trait (here: the ability to assess treatment claims). Therefore, any subset of the items administered to an individual should yield the same estimate of ability. Testing of multidimensionality can be done by comparing person locations estimated based on two subsets of items taken from the questionnaire. We will test this by identifying the two most divergent subgroups of the items and comparing these in independent t-test comparisons of person locations. A threshold of 5% significant t-tests will be considered acceptable, i.e., about 5%

is expected to be significant by chance. Theoretical assumptions about unidimensionality will also be considered.

Local dependency, i.e., the extent to which an element has a bearing on responses to other elements, will also be explored using the residual correlation function in RUMM2030. A residual correlation between 0.2 and 0.3 above the average of all items residual correlations would be considered potentially problematic. Theoretical assumptions about such correlation will also be considered.

Revision of items

As shown above, Rasch analysis is a useful tool for diagnosing problems with the MCQs. Revisions can be made to improve fit, either by revising the MCQs or by deleting them.

Sub-study 3: Piloting a second draft of the questionnaire

Based on the results of the Rasch analysis in sub-study 2, we will consider MCQs that show signs of suboptimal fit for repair or deletion. For those concepts where there are already validated questions (results from sub-study 1), we will include two MCQ, for concepts without validated questions, we will include three MCQ. In the final questionnaire (after this second piloting of the questionnaire), the questionnaire will be reduced to only having two MCQs per key concept and we will choose the ones with the best psychometric properties.

The second draft of the questionnaire will also include questions about intended behaviour and attitudes towards assessing treatment claims. These questions have not previously been tested in our setting.

All questions will be in Norwegian. The questions from the Claim Evaluation Tool have been translated from English to Norwegian by a language specialist associated with the IHC's working group. The questionnaires will also include questions about the participants' age, gender, previous level of education, previous training in scientific method or evidence-based medicine, motivation for studying health sciences, and immigrant background.

Description of eligible participants and administration of the questionnaires

The questionnaire will be administrated electronically using nettskjema.no, a survey solution developed and hosted by the University of Oslo (nettskjema@usit.uio.no). Eligible participants will be second-year nursing students who participate in the EBHC course in weeks 33 through 35 and who willingly chooses to answer the questionnaire. Lecturers on the EBHC course at OsloMet received information about the study from the first author (IKOE) at a seminar at the end of May 2022. The lecturers were encouraged to motivate the students to participate in the study and all attendees were given access to the slides describing the study after the seminar. The course managers of the EBHC

course gave us, the researchers, written consent to use parts of the first lecture day to obtain answers to the cross-sectional survey.

Recruitment

Participants will be recruited during week 32, 2022, by posting information about the study, in the university's password protected learning management system "Canvas". In addition, the students will receive oral information about the study by the first author (IKOE) during the first lecture day on 15 August and they will be given approximately 20 minutes to sign the content form and complete the questionnaire. Students who do not wish to participate can read the syllabus in the time set aside to respond to the survey.

Sample-size

The entire cohort of nursing students who take the EBHC course in weeks 32 to 35 will be invited to participate in the survey, approximately 350 students. There is no gold standard for sample size in Rasch analysis, but it should be about 150 participants per background factor for which DIF is tested. For example, 150 men and 150 women. However, there are few men studying to be nurses and this may affect the generalisability of the results to male nursing students.

Analyses

We will perform Rasch analysis as described in sub-study 2.

We will also perform exploratory analyses to assess the background variables association with the scores on the questionnaire. We hypothesise that students with previous training in scientific method or evidence-based medicine do better than those without, and that there will be little to no differences between genders, based on findings from earlier surveys (Austvoll-Dahlgren et al., 2020a; Oxman et al., 2017). In addition, we want to explore whether there are any differences in score between students from different study specializations and students with or without an immigrant background.

Sub-study 4: Preliminary assessment of learning outcome

We will perform analyses to assess possible learning outcomes from the EBHC course in an uncontrolled before-after study. This approach cannot rule out a number of explanations for achievement differences (Pressley et al., 2006). However, uncontrolled before-after studies can be justified when they act as pilots before more robust evaluations are carried out (Goodacre, 2015; Pressley et al., 2006), to establish whether there is an effect worth investigating and how large this might be.

Sample size calculation

We will analyse the power, and thus the sample size needed, to estimate the percentage of students who understand each of the key concepts in the questionnaire. We will also analyse the power to detect differences in the mean total score on the questionnaire before the EBHC course compared to

the mean total questionnaire score after the EBHC course. We assume that there will be a no non-response to the MCQs because all questions will be mandatory. We will report 95% confidence intervals for all estimated quantities.

In the power calculation, we will take into account that if the participants make random guesses on both MCQs for a given key concept, we expect that $\frac{1}{4^2} \times 100\% \approx 6\%$ of the participants "understand" that concept by chance.

Description of eligible participants and administration of the questionnaires

The questionnaires will be administrated electronically using nettskjema.no, a survey solution developed and hosted by the University of Oslo (nettskjema@usit.uio.no). Eligible participants will be bachelor students in health sciences who participate in the EBHC course in during autumn 2022 (approximately 800 students) and who willingly chooses to answer the questionnaire. Teachers on the EBHC course at OsloMet received information about the study from the first author (IKOE) at a seminar at the end of May 2022. The teachers were encouraged to motivate the students to participate in the study and all attendees were given access to the slides describing the study after the seminar.

Recruitment

Participants will be recruited before each EBHC course held autumn 2022, by posting information about the study in the university's password protected learning manage system "Canvas" one to three days before the course starts. In addition, the students will receive oral information about the study by the first author (IKOE) at the first lecture day and they will be given approximately 20 minutes to sign the content form and complete the questionnaire. Students who do not wish to participate can read the syllabus in the time set aside to respond to the survey.

Towards the end of the EBHC courses, information about the after-test will be announced in "Canvas". Students who participate in the baseline survey will be contacted towards the end of the EBHC course via e-mail and provided with a link to the follow-up survey. An e-mail reminder will be sent after one week.

Multiple-choice questions

The before-after study will include two MCQ from the Claim Evaluation Tool database related to five key concepts from the IHC framework that is included in "Behind the headlines" and four MCQ from two key concepts that we expect students to become familiar with during the EBP course.

Each MCQ will be scored as correct or incorrect and any missing answers will be treated as incorrect, both before and after the EBHC course. A participant will be considered to understand a concept if they answer both MCQs correctly for that concept. We will estimate the proportion of students that understands each concept both before and after the EBHC course using a generalised linear model. We will set cut-off values according to the proportion of students who receive 50% correct answers, and the proportion of students who receive 80% correct answers both to the 14 MCQs and to each of the

seven key concepts. The cut-off values are the same as those used by the IHC project in a cluster randomized trial in Uganda (Nsangi et al., 2017), with a criterion-referenced standard based on a combination of Nedelsky's and Angoff's methods (Davies et al., 2017).

Intended behaviour and attitudes

For questions related to intended behaviour and attitudes, the responses will be dichotomised, i.e., very difficult or difficult vs. very easy or easy, and very unlikely or unlikely vs. very likely or likely. We will compare the number and percentage for each of the dichotomised response options before and after the EBHC course using a generalised linear model.

Exploratory analyses

Exploratory analyses will be conducted to investigate the association between participants' characteristics and their questionnaire scores. We hypothesise that students with previous training in scientific method or evidence-based medicine do better than those without, and that there will be little to no differences between genders, based on findings from earlier surveys (Austvoll-Dahlgren et al., 2020a; Oxman et al., 2017). In addition, we want to explore whether there are any differences in change scores between students from different study specializations and students with or without an immigrant background. We will use a generalised linear model to identify which variables can explain the variation in the participants' questionnaire scores.

Outcomes

Based on the above, the primary and secondary outcomes related to the before-after study will be as follows:

Primary outcomes

- Changes from start to end of the three-week EBHC course in proportion of students receiving 50% correct answers on the 14 MCQ and on each of the seven key concepts, and proportion of students receiving 80% correct answers.

Secondary outcomes

- Difference in mean change-score of MCQ from start to end of the three-week EBHC course.
- Proportion of changes in intended behaviour (unlikely vs. likely) and attitudes (difficult vs. easy) from start to end of the three-week EBHC course.
- Exploratory analyses to assess the background variables association with the change scores on the questionnaire.

In addition, we will perform psychometric testing of the questionnaire, as described in sub-study 2.

Ethical considerations

Data in sub-studies 1 and 2 were collected anonymously without personal data or indirect personal data. According to Norwegian Centre for Research Data's (NSD) guidelines, approval from them was therefore not necessary. We applied for approval of the sub-studies 3 and 4 by the NSD (Reference number 935258) in June 2022, and the survey was approved on 28 July 2022. All data will be analysed anonymous and collected email addresses will be replaced with ID numbers and then deleted. For all sub-studies, we will follow the research ethics guidelines at OsloMet

(<https://ansatt.oslomet.no/planlegging-oppstart-forskningsprosjekt>). Results will be disseminated via an open-access journal and conference presentations. The main findings will be made publicly available through the website <https://bakoverskriftene.oslomet.no/> and other relevant channels.

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